

Rural Marketing “Rural Marketing is Real Marketing”

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Abstract

Definition and domain-related issues of ‘rural marketing’ need further explanation and revision. Often, rural marketing is equated with shopping by multinationals in rural India. The existing literature in rural marketing has uncritically used the concepts, theories, models, and frameworks of the mainstream marketing discipline. So far, farm marketing has failed to create its proprietary concepts, theories, frameworks, and distinct vocabulary. As a result, agricultural marketing cannot claim the status of a separate subdiscipline within the wider marketing discipline. I provide a review of the extant work in rural marketing and its relationship on mainstream market marketing literature. I argue that agricultural marketing must find its distinct prospect before theory construction can begin in the field. After studying the literature on marketing and economic development, I propose that the development of rural people should be the perspective of agricultural marketing. In this paper, I suggest a field and definition of rural marketing and suggest several potential areas for theory construction to begin on the subject. Rural marketing holds the promise of delivering a better standard of living to rural people. We cannot ignore the developmental role that marketing should perform when the large section of Indian populace in rural areas is underdeveloped.

Keywords: rural marketing; developmental marketing; marketing for development; marketing and economic development

Objective

- To develop an insight into rural marketing regarding different concepts and basic practices in this area.
- To discuss the challenges and opportunities in the field of Rural marketing.
- To Roadblocks of Indian Rural Markets.

Introduction

The term ‘rural marketing’ has gained wider currency in both academic and corporate worlds in India. Business organizations have frequently used the word in their marketing rhetoric, while, academics have written glut of textbooks on the subject. This bears evidence of the growing interest in the trend called rural marketing in various business schools. However, it should be made clear in the beginning that this phenomenon of rural marketing is specific to the Indian context. A literature search on two e-databases, Ensco and Proquest, with ‘Rural Marketing’ as keyword produced one and four search results, respectively. An analysis of the contents of several

textbooks on rural marketing (e.g., Dogra and Human 2008; Gopaldaswamy 1997; Kasha and Rout 2006; Krishnamacharyulu and Ramakrishnan 2002; Rajagopal 1998; Velayudhan 2002) shows that the meaning of rural marketing has grown over the past six decades. Kashyap and Raut (2006) have listed three distinct phases in the development of rural marketing, during which the term changed its meaning and intention. In the first phase, pre-nineteen sixties, rural marketing was synonymous with agriculture marketing. In the second phase, from the nineteen sixties to nineteen ninety, the marketing of agricultural inputs and marketing of non-farm rural product was considered as rural marketing. In the post-liberalization period, with rising incomes and burgeoning middle class across the country, various companies focused on tapping the rural markets. The literature, then, tried to convince marketers to explore the market potential of hitherto untouched rural markets (e.g., Bijapurkar 2003; Nabi and Raut 1995; Singh 1992). Rural marketing, now in the post-liberalization period, predominantly referred to the marketing of fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) and consumer durables in rural areas. Various conferences organized on the rural marketing themes and articles written on the subject in the post-liberalization period (e.g., Nabi and Raut 1995; Singh 1992) brings out the popular understanding that rural marketing is about multinationals and big companies marketing their goods and services in rural areas.

Review of Literature

- Hamilton (1965) studied the US market from the year the 1860s forward and noted that marketing was of limited importance in developing economies, as production and consumption were not separated temporally or spatially.
- Shelbina (1965) pointed out the tendency of manufacturing firms to overlook marketing for production considerations.
- Preston (1968) suggested that economic development required the transformation of marketing activities concerning market structures, product variety and volume, and marketing management behaviour. He showed that countries with higher percentages of the population working in commercial marketing activities also had higher gross domestic products.
- Nielsen (1974) studied the impact of marketing communication on consumption in underdeveloped countries. The author countered the theory that suggested that commercial communications shifted money from savings to consumption, making it difficult for a developing society to invest in production facilities. The author stated that the commercial communications and consumption relationship was modified by four factors: the wealth of audiences, degree of product differentiation, extent innovation in communications, and the degree to which the products involved were essential rather than a luxury.
- Prahalad (2005) argues that the poor can be profitable and exhorts the multinationals to do business with them. He warns, however, that the existing knowledge and business model were inadequate for these markets of the poor. He emphasized the need for unconventional thinking and new knowledge to cater to these markets. The case studies that he has provided do merit the attention of both academic and practitioners to create such a new knowledge.

Meaning and Definition of Rural Marketing

The term ‘rural marketing’ used to be an umbrella term for the people who dealt with agricultural products in one way or other. This term got a separate meaning and value after the economic revaluation in India after 1990. So, before trying into the other aspects of rural marketing, let us discuss the development of this city in different parts which are briefly described here.

Part I (Before 1960)

Rural marketing referred to the selling of rural products in rural and urban areas and agricultural inputs in rural shops. It was treated as synonymous to ‘agricultural marketing’. Agricultural produces like food grains and technical inputs like cotton, oilseeds, sugarcane etc. occupied the central place of analysis during this period. The supply-chain activities of firms supplying rural inputs and of artisans in rural areas received secondary attention. The local marketing of products like bamboo baskets, window, ropes, and door frames, small agricultural tools like ploughs by traders like black smiths, carpenters, cobblers, and pot makers was emphasized in general. This was an unorganized market where all Banias and Mahajan (local business people) dominated this market.

Part II (1960 to 1990)

In this era, the green revolution resulted from scientific farming and transferred many of the poor villages into prosperous business centres. As a result, the demand for rural inputs went up, especially in terms of wheat and paddies. Better irrigation facilities, use of high yield variety seeds, soil testing, pesticides, fertilizers and deployment of machinery like harvesters, powder tillers, threshers etc. changed the rural scenario. In this context, marketing of agricultural inputs took the importance. Two separate lots of activities had emerged- during this period ‘marketing of agricultural inputs’ and the conventional “Agricultural Marketing”. During this stage, the marketing of rural products received considerable attention in the general marketing framework. The formation of agencies like Khaki and Village Industries Commission, Viridian Cooperative Societies APCO Fabrics, KRIBHCO, IFFCO, etc., and also the personal attention government had paid to promote these products were responsible for this upsurge. Village industries flourished and products like handicrafts, handloom textiles, safety matches, soaps, crackers etc. hit the urban market on a large scale from rural areas.

Part III (After the Mid 1990s)

The products which were not given attention so far during the two earlier periods were that of marketing of household consumables and durables to the rural markets due to obvious reasons. The economic health of the country was as such that the rural people were not in a position to buy these kinds of products. Secondly, our market was in a close health, and we never allowed companies (foreign) to operate in the Indian market. But we lifted the ... and opened up the economy.

Consequently, companies started flourishing in India. The small villages/hamlets were widely scattered making reach difficult and expensive consequences. Rural markets were seen as an adjunct to the urban market and conveniently ignored. However, since the 1990s, India’s industrial sector had gained in strength and maturity. Its addition to GNP increased substantially. A new service sector had emerged signifying the metamorphosis of agricultural culture into an industrial society.

Meanwhile, due to the development programs of the central and state governments, service organizations and socially responsible business groups like Mafatlal, Tats, Birla’s, Gekas and others, the rural area witnessed all-round socio-economic progress. The economic reforms additional accelerated the process by introducing competition in the markets. Steadily, the agricultural market has grown for household consumables and durables. Rural marketing represented the distinct emergent activity of attracting and serving rural markets to fulfil the needs and wants of persons, homes and occupations of rural people. As a result of the above study, we are in a position to define rural marketing **“Rural marketing can be seen as a function which manages all those actions involved in stimulating, assessing and converting the purchasing power into an effective**

demand for specific products and assistance, and moving them to the people in rural area to create satisfaction and a standard of living for them and thereby achieves the goals of the organization”.

Factors Contributing to the Change in the Rural Market

Green revolution

The substantial attention accorded to agriculture during the successive five-year plans has helped in improving agricultural productivity. Adoption of new agronomic methods, multiple cropping, selective mechanization, the inclusion of cash crops and development of allied activities like dairy, fisheries and other commercial activities have helped in increasing disposable income of rural consumers. Over 75 per cent of villages in India has been electrified. There is also a shift from rain dependence to irrigation. Farmers are getting a high return for their cash and food crops. In the whole process, the dependence on seasonality has reduced, and in recovery, there has been increasing disposable income. By observing this scenario, India's one of the largest giant Hindustan Lever Ltd. has entered into the rural market for more penetration through the operation 'Bharat'. Since December 1999, HLL has transferred out to 35,000 villages, 22 million households and spent Rs. 20 crore. This has been one of the biggest sampling exercises in recent times conducted by a big business house.

Emerging Role of Bio-Tech. in Indian Agriculture Sector

It is obvious from the facts that Indian agriculture is trailing in terms of yield when balanced with leading countries of the world. Countries like the USA, Germany, Israel and Canada have achieved high yield in agriculture product, but countries like India, Nigeria and Brazil are having agriculture yield much lower than the international average. The major variation created in this respect is the use of the importance of biotechnology. Biotechnology has an essential role to play in so far as the enhancement of agriculture yield is concerned. For instance, the yield of wheat in the USA per hectare is almost three times more than that of India, and the yield of sugar cane is two and half times more if matched with the Indian yield of sugar cane per hectare. These advanced countries have been making extensive use of bio-technology, whereas in developing countries the concept is not yet very popular. When we are living in the era of globalization, everything is becoming globally competitive and therefore, we cannot live in isolation in terms of agriculture yield also. We have to make use of the applications of the bio-technology in agriculture sector both in terms of generating variety seeds and cropping the same in compliance with the theories of biotechnology. Our farmers, who are normally not aware of this fact, have to be educated and the responsibility lies on the shoulders of researchers, scientists, administrators and the policy makers of the country. It will provide more discretionary income in the hands of the rural farmers.

Rural communication

Around 50 per cent of the villages are today connected by all-weather roads and can be accessed throughout the year. But there are states, which are almost 100 per cent connected with the metal roads. Road networking, besides improving the mobility of rural consumers, has increased their exposure to products and services. By watching such a scenario in these areas, Korean consumer durable companies have decided to look beyond their noses. They are now placing their bets on rural markets. Two mountains, namely LG and Samsung, have already made their strategies for entering into rural India. As per a survey conducted by Indian Market Research Bureau (IMRB) 77 per cent of the villages are covered by a TV network. Now even villages are going for dish wires, and they have already been enjoying exposure to various products through advertisements.

All the villages are about to be connected with telephone facilities shortly, and already there are some villages which are related to this facility. Apart from this, the internet is not a distant reality. Recently Mr Ram Vilas Aswan, the minister for communication has announced that in the coming days there would be 100 per cent connectivity through telephones in the rural areas. Seeing these types of events and interests of the realties, Tata cellular has previously entered into rural India by making its first entry into Andhra Pradesh. Tata cellular has produced India's largest cellular 'corridor' to give connectivity to non-metro and rural centres.

Development programs

The five-year plans have witnessed massive loans in rural areas in terms of the number of development programs implemented by the central and state Government. These programs have generated incomes to realties and helped them to change their life-styles. Some of these programmers are:

- Intensive Agricultural District Programmed (IADP- Package Programmed)
- Intensive Agricultural Area Programmed (IAAP)
- High Yielding Varieties Programmed (HYVP- Green Revolution)
- Drought Prone Areas Programmed (DPAP)
- Small Farmers Development Agency (SFDA)
- Hill Area Development Programmed
- Operation Flood I, II and III (White Revolution)
- Fisheries Development (Blue Revolution)
- Integrated Rural Development Programmed (IRDPA)
- JawaharlalRojgarYojna (JRY).

These programs are related to agriculture and allied exercises, but there are certain other methods which are specifically meant to raise the standard of the rural people in the field of health, sanitation, education etc. After the beginning of financial reforms in 1991, the Government has been giving special attention to rural India by providing certain developmental schemes for these spaces. Some statements were made by the finance minister in the North Budget 2000 to enrich the existing programmers and to initiate some new schemes for the rural areas like Kinas Credit Cards, Micro Finance and Pardhan Mantri Gramodyog Yojna etc. In the latest budget (2004) focus has been on agriculture and rural development. Since special attention is being given in the union budget through some schemes, and due to progress of economic reforms, debt is declining at a faster pace, and there is a substantial improvement in the per capita income of the people especially in case of the majority of the states of the Indian union. For example, the per capita income of Punjab is Rs. 20,606 followed by Maharashtra Rs. 19,207, Haryana Rs. 18,171, Gujarat Rs. 15,723, Tamilnadu. 13,248 and Karnataka Rs. 11,578 and if we see the middle of 14 states it is Rs. 10,886 at a growth rate of 4.4 per cent. Hence, we can see that today, developments are taking place immediately in all avenues of life and rural areas are no deviation to this. Improved foundation facilities, economic liberalization, the renewed emphasis on agribusiness and small industries, fast-changing agricultural technology, the scope for commercialization of farming, greater budgetary provision for rural people are few reasons to mention.

Moreover, psychological, various socio-cultural and administrative aspects of rural life are also changing. Rural people today are less attached, less fatalistic to religious ideas, getting more individualistic, achievement-oriented and hopeful than before. All this has opened up new vistas for the marketers of Millennium at most limited in the states, which are starting in per capita income with sustained growth, like Punjab, Haryana, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Gujarat, Delhi and Western UP etc.

Perspective for Rural Marketing

The extant work in rural marketing has used the theories, models, concepts, vocabulary, and frameworks of commercial marketing. While there should not be any artificial barriers to adopting concepts and tools from the mainstream marketing literature, but without a theoretical basis or a perspective of its own, blind adoption of marketing theories would create an identity crisis for rural marketing and smother the progress of the nascent field. So far, rural marketing has remained resigned merely to a context for the application of commercial marketing knowledge. As a result, rural marketing has not created its vocabulary, concepts, and ideas. The field of rural marketing is yet to gain a wider acceptance of the global academic community as a field of scholarly research, and it is yet to have its scholarly peer-reviewed journal as a repository of the first kind of knowledge. I foresee no significant progress of rural marketing as a separate stream of inquiry within the marketing discipline until it finds its distinct perspective. The development perspective has existed for over half a century now. I advocate that rural marketing be studied from the development perspective. Rural marketing should attempt to answer how marketing can be used to enhance the development of a rural region and its people. Taking this unique perspective, rural marketing will have a scope for developing its theoretical base, useful concepts, vocabulary, and tools. Industrial marketing and services marketing had also faced a similar identity crisis in their growth trajectory; however, these marketing subdisciplines grew to a respectable position today as they could identify and follow their distinct perspectives. Both the subdisciplines, in the course of their progress, developed their customized theories, concepts, vocabulary, and tools. SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al. 1985) is one such example of contribution from services

Conclusion

After reviewing the literature on marketing and economic development, I have proposed that the development of rural people should be the perspective of rural marketing. The definition of rural marketing provided in this paper presents a clear criterion for identifying a rural marketing activity from amongst various bnm, marketing activities that take place in rural areas. The paper also provides some useful leads for theory-building work to begin in rural marketing.

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